

A phase of life oriented personnel development: a new approach considering the demographic change and the skills shortage in Germany

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1. Introduction

The demographic change in Germany is becoming more and more important for the German industry and especially for public authorities. The number of population with high man-power (age 20-55 years) has already started to decrease in the last year and will tremendously continue in the next decades (2013: 49,5 Mio., 2023: 46,4 Mio., 2033: 40,4 Mio., FSO 2013). Whereas the number of people 55+ years will increase tremendously. This development causes a gap between the number of young people who step on the labour market and the increasing need of young qualified employees especially in consideration of the booming economy in Germany at present. This development called as “the war for talents” will continue and even increase in the next years and will extend the need of qualified staff in Germany especially in the disciplines engineering, health and social work and social welfare (AGE Monitor 2013, GCSA 2013). This development emphasizes that especially small and medium sized companies and institutions of the public authority need innovative personnel development concepts in order to recruit, motivate, bond and develop young qualified employees. Furthermore for the whole staff an elaborated health management concept will be necessary in order to preserve and support the work ability and health especially in consideration of the increasing retirement age (67 years) in Germany (FIIE 2012). The present article gives the example of an institution of the public authority (n=930 employees) with a work emphasis in the area of social care and welfare and its innovative and future based phase of life oriented development concept for the areas recruiting, motivation, bonding, development and health.

2. Methods

A demographic statistical analysis, following the questions: “How old is our staff”? “Which employees from which occupational group and with which qualification will retire at what time?” makes clear that until 2015 22,9% and until 2020 another 22,18% of the staff especially from social-health care and information technology jobs will leave the organization due to retirement reasons (figure 1):

Figure 1: Demographic staff analysis

Figure 1 shows that 24,71% employees in social and health care jobs (25,6 employees per year in average) and 25,12% (10,2 employees per year in average) in information technology jobs will leave the organization until 2015. Moreover the average age of staff in 2010 is 48,8 years and in 2020 it will be 52,3 years. Furthermore there is an average labor turnover rate of 4%. The expected contributions of a personnel development concept in this context are the reduction of the labor turnover rate and the covering of the occupational groups leaving rate (10 people yearly 2010-2015 in IT, 26 in social health care). This is a big challenge because the wanted employees have to have special skills and knowledge. In order to make sure that these new recruited young employees will be able to achieve good working results shortly it will be necessary to build age-differing working teams with experienced older employees and new recruited younger employees.

3. Results

As result a holistic life phase oriented personnel development concept (figure 2) has been established in 2011 which includes recruiting, motivating, bonding and developing employees in their different phases of career steps and accompanying elements of a health management. First results show the success of the concept: In 2013 the average labor turnover rate could be reduced to 2% and 22 employees for social and health care jobs and 11 employees with IT education could be recruited. These are good results in consideration of the short existence and the expected contributions of the concept. In 2014 an employee survey in the organization will be conducted to evaluate the success of the modules from the employees' point of view.

Figure 2: Phase of life oriented personnel development concept